

PATIENTS' PERCEPTIONS OF QUALITY OF CARE IN HEALTHCARE FACILITIES IN THE ANALAMANGA AND BONGOLAVA REGIONS

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ABSTRACT

The Malagasy government's healthcare system aims to provide high-quality, local and affordable care for the entire population. As in other developing countries, users are expressing concerns about the quality and cost of the service provided by healthcare providers. How do users feel about the services provided by healthcare personnel, particularly in public health establishments? The aim of this article is to explore patients' perceptions of the quality of care at different levels of health centers in the Analamanga and Bongolava Regions. From the point of view of health professionals, several causes impacting the quality of their services can be put forward, such as stock-outs of medical consumables, lack of equipment, etc. For beneficiaries, the aspects of the problem of access to quality care vary according to the category of user and the establishment providing the care. Surveys were carried out among patients and their carers in various health establishments, including Basic Health Centres (Centres de Santé de Base - CSB) at the communal level, Regional Reference Hospitals (Centre Hospitalier de Référence Régional - CHR) and University Hospitals (Centres Hospitaliers Universitaires - CHU). Analysis of the data reveals varied patterns of perception among patients, who attach different importance to aspects such as welcome, the quality of medical facilities and services, and the cleanliness and infrastructure of the facility. The results highlight the importance of understanding patients' specific priorities in each care setting and the factors influencing their perception of service quality. They also underline the crucial need for local adaptation initiatives to improve quality of care and respond effectively to patients' needs. This research calls for a more personalized, patient-centered approach to healthcare in Madagascar, highlighting the study's practical implications for improving access to healthcare.

Key words: *Patient perception, Quality of care, Healthcare facility, Healthcare system.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In September 1978, the Declaration of Alma-Ata marked a major turning point by affirming that health goes far beyond the mere absence of disease (Bourgueil *et al.*, 2021), defining it as a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being, thus enshrining health as a fundamental right of every individual. In 1987, the Bamako Initiative was another significant milestone, aiming to reinforce this commitment by proposing concrete strategies to improve the health systems of developing countries, focusing on the universality, efficiency and equity of health services (Moulin, 2013). Madagascar, aware of its specific characteristics, has drawn up its own national

development plan, notably through the Health Sector Development Plan (PDSS) 2020 - 2024, focused on improving access to equitable care for all, including the most marginalized.

This article focuses on assessing the effectiveness of such health policies by highlighting patients' perceptions of the quality of care in health facilities in Madagascar.

The overall aim of the research is to analyze patients' perceptions and experiences of care provision in CHU, CHR and CSB in Madagascar, while examining how these perceptions vary according to the type of facility; this study thus aims to identify areas requiring improvement to ensure quality care provision based on the perceptions of patients themselves.

The hypothesis is that aspects of the problem of access to quality care vary according to the category of user and the facility providing the care.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A systemic approach was adopted, considering organizational aspects, care provision and patient expectations. Data collection was carried out in several healthcare establishments, namely CHU, CHR and CSB. The data were subjected to exploratory and multivariate analysis, including techniques such as Hierarchical Ascending Classification Analysis (HACA), Factorial Data Analysis (FDA), Benchmarking, Ordering and the study of variable Influence and Dominance.

2.1 Presentation of the study area

The Malagasy healthcare system is organized in a pyramidal structure, with health establishments at each administrative level, responsible for providing care to the population. The CSB, located at commune or Fokontany level, provide first aid. In the event of serious illness requiring surgery, patients are referred to the CHD for the districts, or to the CHR for the regional capitals. Cases requiring in-depth exploration are evacuated to the CHU. Madagascar has 22 CHUs, two for each provincial capital other than Antananarivo, which has 12.

For this study, 2 of the 12 Antananarivo UHCs were selected: the Gynecology and Obstetrics UHC (GOB) and the Joseph Ravoahangy Andrianavalona UHC (JRA). Surveys were carried out in 6 departments at CHU GOB and 13 departments at CHU JRA.

At the intermediate level, the study was carried out at CHR Tsiroanomandidy. All patients were received and treated in shared wards.

For basic care, the research focused on the CSB of Ankadinondry Sakay and Tsinjoarivo Imanga in the two rural communes of the Tsiroanomandidy district, Bongolava Region, and on the CSB of Bongatsara, Tsiafahy and Ambalavao located in the 3 rural communes of the Antananarivo Atsimondrano district, Analamanga Region.

2.2 Sampling and data collection

The cross-sectional survey was conducted among users attending the services of two major hospitals, the (CHU GOB) and the (CHU JRA), over a one-week period, using an individual standardized questionnaire exploring the main areas of satisfaction with the quality of care perceived by users. Questions were put to patients, or to their carers if the former were unable to answer; these two categories of people are referred to as users. During their hospitalization, patients are accommodated in hospital wards divided into five categories: the common ward, the third and second categories, the first category and the non-category. The common ward has a minimum of six beds for zero accommodation costs. Chargeable wards start from the second category, while the out-of-category ward is the most expensive.

2.3 Data processing and analysis

The study focuses specifically on correlations between the degree of satisfaction derived from users' responses, their ward categories and the services to which users were admitted. Survey data were entered into Excel and processed using XLSTAT software.

Correspondence Factorial Analysis (CFA) was chosen to analyze discriminations and correlations of variables, in order to classify users and analyze their perceptions of quality of care in university hospitals.

In addition, CAH was used to group patients into homogeneous groups, to be confirmed by AFD. This AFD made it possible to determine the variables that best explained patients' membership of each group, thus reinforcing the robustness of the results obtained (Traore *et al.*, 2021).

2.4 Patients' perceptions of the quality of hospital supplies

2.4.1 Benchmarking typology

Following the SFM, the characterization of each group was enriched through a benchmarking analysis; this shed light on the relationship between each group and the variables characterizing the quality of care in university

hospitals, thus highlighting each group's perception of these variables (Table 1). Benchmark values are defined as the best for each class identified.

Table 1 : Variables related to care risk analysis

VARIABLES	CODE	MOBILIZATION
Respondent (Patient/Companion)	ENQ	
Room category	CAT	
Quality of reception	QAC	
Room quality	QCH	
Air and bed quality	QAR	
Cleanliness	PRO	BENCHMARKING
Laboratory tests and Imaging	ANA	
Operating room	BLO	SCHEDULING
Cost of medication	MED	STRATEGIC
Physician quality	QMD	RECTANGLE
Quality of paramedics (nurse/midwife)	QIF	
Food quality	QAL	
Corruption	COR	
Cost of care (surgery...)	COS	
General appearance of the hospital	VUG	

2.4.2 Ordering patient priorities

This step enabled us to prioritize the variables, taking into account the degree of concern constituting the quality of hospital care. Variables with a p-value greater than 0.20 were eliminated, and the lower diagonal part of the correlation matrix was removed. In addition, variable values below the correlation significance level ($|\rho|$) were excluded from the analysis.

$$|\rho| = \frac{t_{\alpha=0,05}}{\sqrt{n - 2 + t_{\alpha=0,05}^2}}$$

where

- t : Student's t test (1.96)
- n : Number of households surveyed (282)
- $|\rho|$: Correlation significance (0.142)

Next, items above the diagonal whose absolute values are above the significance threshold were evaluated and replaced by “x”. Variables with a minimum number at the correlation significance threshold have no value.

By counting the number of “x” per line, and then gradually grouping the variables with the minimum number, we were able to identify the main variables affecting the quality of hospital care.

2.4.3 Strategic rectangle: prioritizing the dominant and influential variables in the evaluation of hospital care quality

Dominance and influence effects were then assessed to identify influential and dominant variables. Inter-variable correlations were used to check the significance and influence of variables from the strategic rectangle. Non-significant variables were eliminated, and the values of “X” and “Y” were calculated. X” values were sorted in descending order, and those above 1 were grouped into influential variables. The values of “Y” were also sorted in descending order, and the highest values were grouped together as the most dominant variables.

$$X = L/p \text{ et } Y = L \times P$$

where

L: Sum of the absolute values of the variables in the row of the correlation matrix

P: Sum of absolute values of variables in column of correlation matrix

3. FINDS

3.1 Characteristics of quality of care at health center level

The characteristics of quality of care are presented by facility category, namely typology, order of priorities and dominant and influential variables.

3.1.1 Typology of users' perceptions at CSB level

Analysis of the (CAH) and (AFD) enabled us to group the observations from each health center into three distinct groups according to their perception of the quality of care (Table 2, Figure 1).

Table 2 : Typology of user perceptions at the CSB level

CSB	Classes			Total
	Class 1	Class 2	Class 3	
Eff.	58	82	60	200
%	29	41	30	100

At the (CSB) level, the results reveal three distinct classes of perception (Figure 1):

- Class 1 "Oriented towards Comfort and the Environment". This class represents 29% of patients surveyed. They attach great importance to air and bed quality, as well as to the cleanliness of the facility; they are also sensitive to the cost of medication and their general perception of the hospital.
- Class 2 "Focused on Hospitality and Quality of Care" (41%). They emphasize the quality of the reception and the room, as well as the quality of the doctors. They are also concerned about the cost of care, particularly surgery.
- Class 3 "Sensitized to Transparency and the Environment" (30%). Patients in this class attach particular importance to air and bed quality, as well as the perception of corruption within the facility. They are sensitive to the quality of the hospital environment.

3.1.2 Typology of user perceptions at the CHR level

Three groups were identified according to their perception of the quality of care (Table 3, Figure 2).

Table 3 : Typology of user perceptions at the CHR level

CHR	Classes			Total
	Class 1	Class 2	Class 3	
Eff.	11	4	5	20
%	55	20	25	100

For (CHR), the results reveal three distinct classes (Figure 02):

- Class 1 "Focused on Quality of Care and Overall Experience": This class represents 55% of the patients surveyed. Patients in this class attach great importance to the quality of the reception, the air and the bed, as well as to the quality of the doctors. They are also sensitive to the cleanliness of the facility.
- Class 2 "Sensitive to Cleanliness and Infrastructure": 20% of patients were categorized in this class. They emphasize the cleanliness of the facility as a determining factor.
- Class 3 "Oriented towards Comfort and Affordability": Class 3 represents 25% of patients. Patients in this class attach great importance to the quality of the room, as well as to the cost of medication.

3.1.3 Typology of user perceptions at CHUJRA and CHUGOB

Three distinct groups were obtained (Table 4, Figure 3).

Tableau 4 : Typology of user perceptions at the CHU JRA and CHUGOB levels

CHUJRA et CHUGOB	Classes			Total
	Class 1	Class 2	Class 3	
Eff.	18	16	37	71
%	25	23	52	100

For hospitals, analysis of the data collected at the CHUJRA and CHUGOB University Hospitals reveals a variety of perceptions among patients, divided into three distinct classes:

Class 1 “Attentive to Comfort and Welcome”: This class represents 25.3% of patients surveyed. Patients in this class attach great importance to the quality of the welcome and the air/bed. They also value the quality of the room and food.

Class 2 “Concerned about Comfort and Welcome”: 22.5% of patients were categorized in this class. Patients in this class emphasize the quality of the room and the welcome they receive. They also consider the quality of food to be a crucial aspect.

Class 3 “Focused on Overall Quality of Care”: The majority of patients, 52.1%, were classified in this category. This class includes patients who attach importance to the quality of the room and food. They also value the quality of reception and doctors.

Figure 1 : Characteristics of Perceptions by Each Observation Class at CSB

Figure 2 : Characteristics of Perceptions by Each Observation Class at CHR

Figure 3 : Characteristics of Perceptions by Each Observation Class at (CHUJRA and CHUGOB)

3.2 Order of priority for quality of care

3.2.1 Prioritization of users at the CSB level

The results of the priority ranking at the CSB level (Figure 04) show that a warm and attentive welcome is considered the most important feature, followed by room and air/bed quality. Cleanliness of the facility and transparency of drug costs are also essential elements for patients. Corruption, on the other hand, is perceived as less of a priority, as is the general assessment of the hospital, which appears at the bottom of the priority list.

3.2.2 User priorities at the CHR level

For the (CHR) (Figure 05), the quality of the room and of the reception are considered the most important features, followed by the cleanliness of the establishment. Air and bed quality, as well as the availability of services such as operating theatres and laboratory analyses, are also top priorities for patients. On the other hand, the cost of medication is perceived as a lower priority, appearing at the bottom of the priority list.

3.2.3 Users' order of priority at CHUJRA and CHUGOB

The results of the priority ranking at the (CHUJRA and CHUGOB) level (Figure 06) revealed the most important characteristics for patients. The results showed that, for patients attending the UHCs, the category of hospital ward was considered the most important feature, closely followed by the quality of the reception and the room. Cleanliness of the facility and the quality of the air and bed are also top priorities for patients. On the other hand, the quality of doctors and food services is perceived as less of a priority, appearing at the bottom of the priority list.

Figure 4 : Prioritization at the Level of CSB

Figure 5 : Prioritization at the level of CHR

Figure 6 : Prioritization at the level of CHUJRA and CHUGOB

3.3 Dominant and influential variables perceived by patients on the quality of care at health facility level

3.3.1 Dominant and influential variables at CSB level

An analysis of the dominant and influential variables for CSBs reveals several factors that influence patient perceptions (Table 5).

3.3.1.1 Dominant and influential variables

These are 3 variables.

- Quality of welcome (4): This was found to be dominant, with high scores for X and Y. This indicates its significant importance in patients' overall perception of CSBs.
- Room quality (3): This represents the quality of hospital rooms. Room quality is a crucial aspect of the patient experience in (CSBs) and strongly influences their overall perception of the facility.
- Drug/cost (2): This underlines the importance of drug costs in patient perceptions. Patients are sensitive to the costs associated with medication, and their perception of the affordability of care influences their experience.

3.3.1.2 Influential variables

- Respondent (Patient): This suggests that being surveyed as a patient may influence patients' overall perception.
- Air and bed quality (2): Although less dominant than the first variables, air and bed quality are important aspects of patient experience in CSBs.

Table 5 : Variables dominantes et influentes sur la qualité de soin au niveau des CSB Dominant and influential variables on quality of care at CSB level

VARIABLES	X = L/P	Y= LxP
Quality of welcome (4)	2,31212994	3,51952116
Room quality (3)	1,79831801	3,24254185
Medication/Cost (2)	1,03983211	2,82631492
Surveyed (Sick)	2,30870332	2,30870332
Air and bed quality (2)	1,32153101	1,81328437

3.3.2 Dominant and influential variables at CHR level

Four dominant and influential variables and 2 influential variables were identified (Table 6).

3.3.2.1 Dominant and influential variables

These are the variables:

- Air and bed quality (1): This variable was identified as dominant, with a high Y score, indicating its significant importance in patient perception. Good air and bed quality are essential to ensure patient comfort and safety in the CHR.
- Quality of welcome (4): Also dominant, this variable represents the experience of welcoming patients to the CHR.
- Operating theatre (4): This variable is also dominant, underlining the importance of the quality of surgical services in patients' perceptions.
- Room quality (4): This variable was also identified as dominant, underlining the importance of inpatient room quality in the overall patient experience.

3.3.2.2 Influential Variables

These are the variables :

- Cleanliness (2), and
- Laboratory Analysis and Imaging Services (4).

This suggests that the cleanliness of the facility and the quality of laboratory analysis and imaging services also impact patients' perceptions, albeit to a lesser extent.

Table 6 : Dominant and Influential Variables on Quality of Care at CHR

VARIABLES	X = L/P	Y= L x P
Air and bed quality (1)	1	2,12818925
Reception quality (4)	1,57735027	1,57735027
Operating room (4)	1,5527708	1,5527708
Room quality (4)	1,45883147	1,45883147
Cleanliness (2)	1	1
Laboratory analysis and imaging (4)	1	1

3.3.3 Dominant and Influential Variables at CHU JRA and CHU GOB

The results highlight the crucial importance of reception quality, accommodation quality, and the category of hospitalization rooms in patients' overall perception of CHUs. They also underline the significant impact of food quality on patient experience (Table 7).

3.3.3.1 Dominant and influential variables

There are 3 dominant variables:

- Reception Quality (4): This variable is dominant, with high scores in both X and Y, indicating its significant importance in patients' overall perception of CHUs.

- Room Category (1): Also dominant, this variable represents the type of hospitalization room. As one of the first aspects patients are exposed to, the room category strongly influences their overall perception of the facility.
- Reception Quality (2): Just like Reception Quality (4), this variable is also dominant, once again highlighting the importance of reception in patients' experience at CHUs.

3.3.3.2 Influential Variables

There are 4 influential variables:

- Room Category (3) and Room Quality (3): Although less dominant than the first two variables, room category and quality remain influential in patients' perception.
- Food Quality (3): Identified as influential, though less dominant than the previous ones, food quality is an important aspect of hospital care quality and influences patient satisfaction.
- Air and Bed Quality (2): This variable is not dominant but still greatly influences patients, particularly regarding the quality of air and beds.

Table 7 : Dominant and Influential Variables on Quality of Care at CHU JRA and CHU GOB

VARIABLES	X = L/P	Y= L x P
Reception quality (4)	1,32508181	8,7073414
Room category (1)	2,71119212	7,39473972
Reception quality (2)	1,98662045	6,93436462
Room category (3)	4,14246272	4,14246272
Food quality (3)	1,02311767	2,6896531
Room quality (3)	2,51015573	2,51015573
Air and bed quality (2)	1,2929179	2,01667513

By understanding these key factors, healthcare facilities can better meet the needs and expectations of their patients, thus improving the quality of care provided at each level of healthcare service, from CSB and CHR to University Hospital Centers CHU JRA and CHU GOB.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Perception Levels on the Quality of Care Provided by Healthcare Services

The analysis of data from various levels of healthcare services reveals diverse perception patterns among patients. The results of the analysis of CSB reveal three distinct classes of perceptions among patients. Class 1 emphasizes comfort and environment, Class 2 focuses on reception and quality of care, while Class 3 is sensitive to transparency and environment (Table 2, Figure 1). These results can be explained by the fact that patients have different expectations and priorities based on their experience in the CSBs. Some patients place more importance on the hospital environment, while others focus more on the quality of care and reception.

At the level of CHR, three distinct classes have also been identified. Class 1 focuses on the quality of care and overall experience, Class 2 on cleanliness and infrastructure, while Class 3 is centered on comfort and financial accessibility (Table 3, Figure 2). Compared to CSBs, CHR patients seem to place more importance on the quality of care and overall experience, as well as the cleanliness and infrastructure of the facility.

For CHU, the results also reveal three distinct classes of perceptions among patients. Class 1 emphasizes comfort and reception, Class 2 is concerned with comfort and reception, while Class 3 focuses on the overall quality of care (Table 4, Figure 3). Compared to CSBs and CHRs, CHU patients seem to be more attentive to the overall quality of care, including room and food quality, as well as the quality of doctors.

The results highlight the diversity of patients' perceptions regarding access to care in different types of healthcare facilities in Madagascar (Beaucourt & Louart, 2011). They also reveal the importance of considering the specific expectations and concerns of patients (Nguyen Thi *et al.*, 2002) when designing and implementing health policies. Patients place great importance on various aspects of their care experience, such as the quality of reception (Geneviève, 2000), the hospital environment (Or *et al.*, 2013), doctors, as well as the cleanliness and infrastructure of the facility. These results underline the necessity for healthcare facilities to provide high-quality

care while considering patients' individual needs and preferences (Setbon, 2000). Additionally, differences in patients' perceptions between different types of healthcare facilities highlight the importance of adapting care delivery strategies based on the local context and specific characteristics of each facility (Chougrani & Ali, 2011). A personalized and patient-centered approach is essential to ensuring patient satisfaction and improving access to healthcare for all (Aldana & Piechulek, 2001).

The strengths of this comparative analysis of patient perceptions in different levels of healthcare services offer a clear presentation of patient expectations. By clearly identifying dominant trends, such as the emphasis on care quality, reception, and infrastructure, this study provides specific improvement avenues for each care context. Furthermore, by highlighting the importance of considering these differences in clinical practice and health policy, this analysis offers potential for generalization and significant practical implications for improving care quality and patient satisfaction. However, subjective data based on patient perceptions can be influenced by unmeasured individual and contextual factors, which may limit the generalization of conclusions, requiring additional study for specific area reports.

4.2 The Crucial Importance of Local Adaptation Initiatives in Building Resilience Against Environmental Hazards

The results offer significant insights for improving healthcare at different levels. By understanding patients' priorities and perceptions, healthcare facilities can adapt their policies and practices to effectively meet the specific needs of their clientele. Ultimately, a better understanding of these factors can help enhance the quality of care provided across the healthcare system, focusing on patient satisfaction and well-being.

Firstly, the analysis of the prioritization of care quality reveals marked differences across various levels of healthcare services. For the CSB, a warm and attentive reception is considered the most important characteristic (Figure 04), while for the CHR (Figure 05), room and reception quality are prioritized (Saizonou *et al.*, 2014). In contrast, for the University Hospital Centers (CHU JRA) and (CHU GOB) (Figure 06), the category of hospitalization rooms is deemed most important (Fraisie *et al.*, 2003). These results highlight the importance of understanding patients' specific priorities in each type of healthcare facility (Petit *et al.*, 2021).

Regarding patients' perceptions of care quality, the analysis of dominant and influential variables highlights key aspects. For the CSB (Table 5), the quality of reception, room quality, and medication costs emerge as dominant factors (Allenet *et al.*, 2009, Le Pogam *et al.*, 2009). For the CHR (Table 6), air and bed quality, reception quality, and availability of services such as the operating room are prioritized (Gentil, 2012). As for the University Hospital Centers (CHU JRA) and (CHU GOB) (Table 7), reception quality, hospitalization room category (Bensafi & El Houari, 2017), and food quality are identified as dominant factors (Melchior *et al.*, 2003).

The strengths of this analysis lie in delving into patients' priorities and perceptions regarding care quality at different levels of healthcare services. By clearly identifying differences between the Community Health Centers (CSB), District Hospitals (CHR), and University Hospital Centers (CHU JRA) and (CHU GOB), the analysis offers valuable insights to improve healthcare delivery. Additionally, the use of statistical analysis methods such as the analysis of dominant and influential variables enhances the robustness of the conclusions by identifying the most significant factors in patients' perceptions.

However, this analysis also presents certain limitations. It primarily relies on self-reported patient data, which could lead to perception biases or socially desirable responses. Moreover, it does not take into account the perspectives of healthcare staff or other stakeholders, which could offer a more holistic view of care quality. Furthermore, the results might be specific to the region studied. A comparative analysis with other studies or validation of results through qualitative methods could strengthen the reliability and validity of the conclusions.

5. CONCLUSION

The study provides valuable insights into the perceptions and priorities of patients regarding the quality of care at different levels of healthcare services in Madagascar. By analyzing data from CSB, CHR, and CHU, distinct perception patterns highlighting patient needs and expectations in each care context were identified. The hypothesis suggesting that "the aspects of the problem of access to quality care vary according to user categories and the care-providing establishment" has been confirmed.

The results emphasize the importance of considering contextual differences and specific patient priorities when designing and implementing health policies. By identifying priority areas such as reception, quality of facilities and medical services, and factors influencing patients' perceptions, this study offers concrete improvement avenues for healthcare facilities in Madagascar. However, it is essential to acknowledge the limitations of this study, including the risk of perception bias in patient data and the need for additional validation of results. Indeed, no assessment of healthcare staff was included.

More effective strategies for ensuring high-quality, patient-centered healthcare nationwide can be developed by integrating the perspectives of patients, healthcare staff, and other stakeholders. The approach

adopted can be expanded at all levels to improve access to care and promote a more personalized patient-centered approach. This approach should, however, consider local adaptation initiatives to improve care quality and effectively meet patients' needs, particularly at the level of CSBs.

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